

Use of Library Resources in Education: A Case Study of GDC Chenani, J&K

Paper Id : 18914 Submission Date : 03/04/2024 Acceptance Date : 11/04/2024 Publication Date : 25/04/2024

This is an open-access research paper/article distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International, which permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided the original author and source are credited.

DOI:10.5281/zenodo.11617692

For verification of this paper, please visit on <http://www.socialresearchfoundation.com/resonance.php#8>

Poonam Sharma

Ex Assistant Librarian
Education
GDC Chenani
Jammu, Jammu and
Kashmir, India

Abstract

The study investigated the use of library by the students of Govt. Degree College Chennai, Udhamapur. The importance of library as an institution has been realized. The study was conducted to understand the services provided by the college library and awareness level among the students.

The data regarding frequency, purpose of library visit, related problems services of the library etc. were obtained and related suggestions were given.

The nature of the study was descriptive. The research of this study considered of all the students of BA, B.Sc, B.Com (major /minor)level students. A sample size of 50 students of the college were selected randomly.

A well structure questionnaires were prepared to generate primary data which were analyzed using quantitative and qualitative techniques.

Keywords

Library Services, Resources, Chenani, Visit, Information.

Introduction

Sir Richard steel has very rightly said " Reading to mind is what exercise to the body".

Education is a process that starts when you are born. Education can be considered as the process of discovering something new that a person does not previously know. It is an essential part of life because it empowers people with knowledge, enables them to contribute to society, earn money, and become independent.

It may be considered as a process of the nourishment of good. qualities, attainment of knowledge and drawing out the inner potentialities of every individual to help in developing and enhancing the physical, moral, social, intellectual, emotional and spiritual powers of the human beings. To ensure that people get a lifelong education library should be made accessible and library services should be made available at all places, to all sections of the society. People seek information from different sources and formats to undertake a variety of jobs and tasks as it is used as information for decision making, discovering new phenomena, developing new techniques and technologies, and improving existing knowledge and theories by shaping human thinking, character building, communication, and the teaching process.

The library is a collection or group of collections of books and other print or non-print material's organised and maintained for reading, consultation and study, research etc.

The library resources are both print and non-print that support information needs. Dictionaries and glossaries, encyclopaedia, handbooks, maps, atlases, bibliographies, common documents, monographs, journals, magazines, newspapers, books, microphones, C.Ds, videotapes, E-books, audio-books etc. are the important library materials used for attaining information and knowledge. The libraries acquire the said audio-video and reading materials organise preserved them and disseminate information to

the users. Hence playing an important role in the development of society. These materials enable users to develop ideas, knowledge and experiences. It also helps the records of human knowledge for easy physical handling storing using and preserving over the years. The material for research skills and productivity. It also helps in providing services to the fresh and regular users. It also helps to connect people to people allows children, younger and elders to stay engaged with the latest updates of the world. It also helps in healthy readership.

The library is an important part of any educational institute as it paves way for the development and progress of the region and helps in shaping the mind set of people to look forward to modernizing and revolutionizing the changes required in the society. It has an important role to play in academics for intellectual progress and basic education that creates an impact on the entire generation. The teaching - learning centers are incomplete without a library. It makes an effective resource for teaching without the biasness of nationality, gender, rate, religion, caste and creation. It opens the mind of all generations and helps in their educational attainment.

Govt Degree College Chenaini

Government. Degree College, Chenani (J&K), aims to nurture student learning, foster faculty research and creative activity, and provide service to the larger community.

The Foundation of the College was laid on 8th March 2019 at the village of Tandhar, Tehsil Chenani, in the Udhampur district, (J&K). A vast area of 97 kanals and 19 marlas was set aside for the construction of the College buildings with all modern and requisite amenities. The first Academic Session of the College commenced on 19th July 2019. The College aims to support the population of the 45 surrounding villages of the Tehsil Chenani.

The College started with a Humanities stream, with 10 subjects supporting 106 students. In 2020, Science streams (with subject combinations in disciplines of Medical, Non-Medical, and subjects in Computer Applications) were added to the offerings. The College promotes lifelong learning, research, creative activity, social and professional responsibility and growth. To meet these activities, the College encourages students to think critically and intuitively across disciplinary boundaries, and to recognize and value diverse perspectives, solving problems creatively with perseverance.

The College is committed to training teachers and students in the application of Educational Technology.

Library of GDC Chenani

The college library is the foundation of college education .It is the hub of college education around which all academic activities revolve. The Library aims at providing necessary information and making them available to all beneficiaries in the appropriate time. The Library supports the academic community in carrying out teaching learning and research activities to the extent within the financial constraints. In Order to inculcate the habit of reading amongst the students, the college has a well-stocked library and well-furnished reading room. All the students, the faculty members and the non-teaching staff have access to the books and the reading room. The college library has a large collection of books ranging from encyclopedias to fiction, text books to journals and reference books, general awareness to competitive books.

The college library is very rich in collection pertaining to different fields viz; medical, non-medical, Arts, humanities etc. The total collection of the library is 6021 which comprises of text books, references, periodicals, journals, magazines of different disciplines like General English, English Literature, Education, Political Science, Sociology, Zoology, Botany, Chemistry, Environmental Science, Computer Application, Mathematics, Physics, Urdu, Geography, Hindi and Dogri.

The college library with its varied collection of newspapers opens a window to the wider world for the students. We plan to subscribe magazines and e-resources shortly.

Library Rules

As per the library rules Books are issued to the students on production of the Library borrower card cum identity card which is issued to him/her at the start of the academic session by the Librarian. In case the card is lost, the student has to bring this to the notice of the Librarian at once to avoid any misuse of the card.

Books lost or damaged in any way are to be replaced by the borrower failing which double the cost of the books are charged. The borrower satisfy himself/herself about the sound condition of the book before leaving the counter.

Students appearing for the University Examinations surrender their Library Card / borrowers card before receiving their roll number slips. Students failing to surrender their card at that time are a fine of Rs. 50/-or more.

Books are issued for a period of 14 days only and fine of ₹ 1/-per day per book is charged after the due date.

Objective of study

The study was conducted to achieve the following specific objectives:

1. To identify the available services in the selected college library.
2. To find out the awareness level among the users.

Review of Literature

Library resources ensure academic integrity among students. In terms of language use and sharing information. DelGuidice (2015) asserts that as part of a larger, multifaceted effort to promote the understanding and utilization of information and technological literacies, academic libraries have a duty to teach students about the values and abilities of academic integrity. Similarly, social presence, e.g., social support, assistance, and empathy, could develop academic integrity among students (Chavez, 2023).

Students believed that because of social support and assistance they received from the library personnel and librarian, they were more confident in language use, especially in sharing important and factual information with their friends, during reporting, presentation, or conversations.

Library services comprise resources, activities, programmes, and instructions to assist customers in meeting their information requirements and making intelligent and effective use of the library's many resources and services. Library services, which provide access to a wide range of information resources, especially electronic resources, encourage academic and research excellence as well as personal development. The collection development strategy of the college library is to provide access to library materials. The college library obtains a database collection for reference as well as consortia to aid users. Aside from specialised ideas in the development of a clear and well-defined strategy, journal selection and subscriptions satisfy the demands of users and vital requests from reference enquiries.

Fagan et al. (2022) highlighted the role of librarians in education and learning. Non-librarian faculties think that "librarians' number 1 priority is helping the student," "they have knowledge practical to them," "librarians are easy to talk with," and "librarians help me search more effectively."

In a similar vein, Halloumeh and Jirjees (2016) study on the use of e-resources against print journals in academic libraries in Abu Dhabi discovered that the majority of respondents (65 percent) preferred electronic journals to printed journals. Respondents, on the other hand, urged that libraries not relinquish their print acquisitions.

Lee (2007) and Sharma and Kumar (2016) agree that electronic and print versions should coexist, and that a hybrid collection is a reasonable option because it gives users more access options between the two formats.

Methodology

For the proposed study, systematic methods of reflection thinking and various other procedures are implied. The information and data are collected from numbers of primary and secondary sources such as journals, information brochures, books pamphlets, newspapers, websites etc. Keeping in view the objectives of the study, a structured questionnaire was framed for the purpose of data collection. About 50 questionnaires were circulated among the users. Besides this, self observation and self-investigation methods were also used to study the information sources and services. The collected data was tabulated and analysed systematically.

Sampling

For the study, survey of 25% students of the said college i.e 50 users were selected for the sample from sem II, IV and VI of under graduates.

Sampling Technique to be Used

Stratified sampling technique was used for the selection of respondents.

Tools Used The questionnaire method was applied for the present study to collect the necessary primary data for evaluation and assessment.

Result and Discussion The study is based on 50 respondents who were the students of GDC Chenani out of these 22% were males and

Source survey by author 2023

Frequency of Library Visit

Source survey by author 2023

Frequency of library visit of the students has also been looked into. It's interesting to note that 36% respondents visit the library once, 30% visited 2-3 times a week but 20% students do not visit the library even once.

Purpose of library use

Source survey by author 2023

It's amazing to note that not even a single student uses the library resources for pleasure. Which clearly indicates the stressful academic environment where the interest of the students towards exploring. The academic literature is not generated and 94% work using the library for reading purpose are just concerned about passing the exam.

Purpose of last visit to library

Source survey by author 2023

When ask about their last visit to library 40% visited to borrow books and 22% to concerned reference books and again 22% when to prepare notes. only 6% student had gone to read newspapers and magazines but not a single case was identified to have used CD ROM. Though the college library was planning to install the computer but at the time of survey it didn't have the system but the library did have CDs related to e-books, catalogue etc. The awareness regarding CD-ROM is also provided in the library. So that these resources are used by them in their Pcs and personal laptops.

Though the reference books are always used out of the interest of the students to look for material beyond general books prescribed in the syllabus but they were guided by the teachers to look into the particular book which placed in reference section for examination purpose otherwise not had personal interest in exploring reference section.

Problem in finding information

Source survey by author 2023

Having access to library resources is usually unknown to these undergraduate students through the library resources are available in their institution where they studied prior to their admission in the college. Which clearly reflect the lack of training at a younger age in consulting the library resources.

The above figure clearly indicates that 54% enquire from the Librarian/assistant for searching the information though only 16% browse the information. Which reflect their inclination towards the e-resource which can be sought even from the mobiles when links are provided to them from the library official. Non is using catalogue or computer as it's very clear from the above discussion that the library neither has the computer nor the catalogue system. 8% students do not bother to even ask and give up getting information.

Library rules

Source survey by author 2023

When ask about following the library rule. 88% agreed that they follow the rules of library, but 4% response agreed that they do not follow the rules set up by the institution in library.

Option of using public library

Source survey by author 2023

A very encouraging information was sought from the survey that 12% respondents were ready to use the public library if available nearby for extra reading after college hours.

Reading Interest

Source survey by author 2023

The students interest was also enquired for reading. Where in 70% agreed that their interest in reading the newspapers and magazines related to sport ,literature geopolitics, art and culture. where as 8% were interested in fiction and another 8% person interested in non -fiction, where as another set of 8% did not have any specific interest. When asked about wether they find books in college library, 54% responded that they found them sometimes. where as 32% always found the books of their interest.

Opening hours of library

Source survey by author 2023

22% respondents wanted the college library to remain open even after college hours, which is as indicative of their interest in library after they get free from the studies.

What library Mean.

Source survey by author 2023

When the respondents were asked to explain what library means to them 58% feel that it was a quite place where they could concentrate on their study. 4% wanted to get out of it as soon as possible, 10% felt they could get together with their friends in the library and 20% had no reason to specify.

Services provided by the library

Source survey by author 2023

The college library as per the respondents provided the reference services (Informed by 72% students)18% students indicated that user awareness services were also provide by library and only 2% agreed that browsing services were also given.

Conclusion

Since the college library was established 5 years back still it is well equipped with study material but automation is still not executed. As at present the college running in the hostel building of Girls high school as is under construction where in after April 2024 the shifting of college will start and library will get it's due accomodation with all modern facilities and then the automation process will take place. At present the library administration is in the process of purchase of library software to make morden setup for the students and faculty. Looking into the above efforts of the institute it clearly indicates that the place like Chenani will cater to be the academic needs and interests of the young productive minds for more and new knowledge making them ready for a bright academic future to make them at par with the national and international information.

Suggestions for the future Study

1. There should be a library class in schools in which the Higher Secondary students should be given theoretical knowledge of resources available in the library of their Institute and then taken to the library encouraging them to find out the books at their own.
2. Students should be trained to frequently visit library, use the different sections independently.
3. The library infrastructure should have more than one computer so that the CD ROM can be used by the students in the library and can discuss with their concerned teachers regarding the availability of literature, what more to look for once the CD is taken home it mostly comes back without being used and but ever the queries that come in there mind does not get transpired to the teacher to reach a successful ending of information gathering.
4. The inclination of the students towards browsing the Academic link is a healthy sign which should be taped by the Institute by providing good hardware and software in the library. So that it helps to generate their interest in Academia by understanding the digital cataloging for easy access to related literature.
5. The study has clearly indicated that there is no student who visit the library for pleasure but are coming only for preparing for the examination. Though they have varied interest in reading related to the various categories. This is highly reflective of their approach toward the library visit. This requires the conditioning of the young mind to divert them towards the library resources which are of their interest from a recreational point of view rather than a stress oriented mind set of qualifying the exam. Library of the institute need to be projected as recreational activity where the student can come to explore their interest, there stress and have a good pass time. The concept of institutional library needs to be reviewed and popularized by awareness activity within the institutes and its public place. We need to catch the young minds and direct them towards positive arenas of life.
6. The institutional library must equipt itself with the books, magazines etc. which are of the interact of the students besides curriculum books to foster the increased frequency of visit.
7. There is requirement of a library which is open for long hours to Cater to the interest of the student during their free time (after college hours and holidays) as a college is the only higher educational institute within the region and can best provide services to the public as

well. Since there are many government officers, Banks, Post Office, Government schools etc where people have to shift away from the family. Hence, this library can provide them the best pass time after working hours and during holidays such a practice will also inculcate the interest among the locals towards the library resources which will help in the development of the region.

8. This library can also be used for the demonstration by the exports where they can teach the surrounding population by having programmers of how the library sources can used for the economic and regional development.

References

1. Chavez JV (2023). Assessing online academic integrity and humanized teaching in Zamboanga Peninsula Polytechnic State University. *Journal of Multidisciplinary in Social Sciences* 19(1): 9–17.

2. Chavez JV, Lamorinas DD (2023). Reconfiguring assessment practices and strategies in online education during the pandemic. *International Journal of Assessment Tools in Education* 10(1): 160–174

3. Library Resources and their Contributions in Academic Study and Research: A Study from the Colleges of Eastern Uttar Pradesh . (2023). *Library Progress (International)*, 43(1), 87–100. <https://doi.org/10.48165/bpas.2023.43.1.10>

4. Fagan JC, Ostermiller H, Price E, Sapp L (2022). Faculty perceptions of academic librarians: Experts, connectors, and resource stewards. *New Review of Academic Librarianship* 28(1): 79–116. doi: 10.1080/13614533.2020.1819354

5. Sharma, P.C & Kumar, R (2016). Usage preference of e-publications by health professionals of Dayandnad Medical College and Hospital, Ludhiana (Punjab). *Journal of Library and*

information Technology, 36(2),88-92.

6. www.gdcchenani.in

7. Information collected from the library of govt. Degree College Chenani, Udhampur Accessed on 1 March 2024.